

**FORMATION OF HOUSING AND COMMUNAL SECTOR
ACTIVITIES IN UZBEKISTAN AND THEORETICAL AND
METHODOLOGICAL ASPECTS OF THEIR MANAGEMENT**

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8072966>

It is known from world experience that the level of development of any society increases through the development of "human resources" as a means of increasing the level of well-being and well-being of its citizens. Today, the indicators of the international evaluation structures that assess the state of development of countries are not only based on the economic indicators, but also the indicators of the social development of the society are taken into account. Because the indicators of social development reflect changes as a result of the country's economic development, and through these indicators it is possible to evaluate its general state of development.

It is appropriate to classify housing and communal services based on specific characteristics and features as follows (Table 1):

Table 1
Classification of housing and communal services¹

Character and characteristics	Service types
According to the nature of the subject of production of services and the object of consumption	Intangible services (guarding, cleaning and other services) Material services (repair of places used by the public, sanitary and technical equipment, means of communication, etc.)
According to the functional content of the provided services	Personal services (maintenance and maintenance of houses and other services) Services that create new products (construction of residences and other services based on individual orders of residents) Services that restore the consumer properties of products in use (repair services of residential premises, residential equipment) Intellectual services (advertising, design and other services)
According to the attitude towards consumption and accumulation	Paid services (payments for services made by consumers) Free services (services implemented at the expense of budget funds)
According to the form of consumption	Individual services (repair of residences, etc.) Shared services (water supply, sewage, maintenance of public areas,

¹Developed by the author.

	etc.)
According to the level of service	Standard services for social housing (municipal). (social-private) services to ensure the comfort of living High-quality (for economically stable consumers) services

With the development of market relations, the scope of services provided to the population is expanding further through the involvement of private enterprises in the field of housing and communal services. In world practice, there is a trend of segmentation (commercial and non-commercial), which is the basis for segmenting the market based on common features of the services provided.

The fact that the elasticity of the demand for the services offered by the market of housing and communal services is very low, that is, the possibility of choosing these types of services or determining the volume of consumption is limited, requires a structural study of the offered services market.

Based on the characteristics of socio-economic relations in the field of housing and communal services, it is appropriate to study the market by dividing it into two segments. Because this service sector simultaneously covers the market of housing and communal services (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. Classification of housing and communal economy market²

Housing and communal economy market includes residential land market, housing finance market, housing market and communal economy market, and all these markets are combined with housing and communal economy services market. not directly connected. The market of housing services within the housing market and the market of communal services within the market of communal services together form the market of housing and communal services.

²Developed by the author.

The housing and communal services market provides consumers (residents) with the following two groups of services offered by the housing services market and the communal services market (Figure 2).

1. Services provided by the housing services market:

- housing fund management services;
- services for the operation of the housing fund;
- housing fund maintenance, maintenance and current repair services;
- elevator maintenance and repair services;
- household waste removal services;
- maintenance services of common property and front areas;
- perfect repair services of residences;
- residential rental services;
- housing insurance services;
- emergency repair services in the housing stock.

2. Services provided by the utility market:

- water supply and sewage services;
- heat supply services;
- electricity supply services;
- natural gas supply services;
- convenience of living services;
- utility services.

The proposed classification of the housing and communal services market was developed not to cover the full range of services provided by the housing and communal economy, but to facilitate the practical activity of determining the boundaries of services in the market of specific regions and products.

Figure 2. Classification of services provided to consumers in the housing and communal services market³

The types of services provided in the housing and communal services market can be divided into two groups⁴:

Group 1 services- pure services aimed at satisfying clearly visible needs. Services in this group are performed by providing specific works or services based on the needs of consumers, and in the provision of this group of services, there is a certain level of (conditional) competition in the service market.

Group 2 services- resource providing services. The services in this group are carried out in the form of the supply of resources (natural gas, electricity, cold and hot water, sewage removal, etc.) to the consumer for which the price is clear, and in the provision of services in the segment of this group, the services market is natural monopoly exists.

³Developed by the author.

⁴Department of urban economy: educational department. number of authors: subed. Created by RJ Sirajdinov. M.: Knorus, 2009. Page 48.

In our country, the market of housing and communal services and the process of establishing and managing enterprises operating in this market are being carried out side by side with the ongoing structural changes. However, reforms in this area are progressing more slowly than the structural changes in other branches and sectors of the national economy. The main reason for this situation is the low profitability of the sector, based on the fact that the prices of the services provided in the field of housing and communal services and the prices of the supplied communal resources are relatively cheap based on the socio-economic status of the users of the services. Under the influence of the indicated factors, market relations in the field are being implemented at a low pace, As a result of the work being carried out, necessary changes are taking place in the mutual relations and management forms of enterprises operating in the field of housing and communal services, as well as institutions that regulate and coordinate their activities. This, in turn, has a positive effect on the efficiency and stability of enterprises operating in the field based on different forms of ownership.

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